

Unveiling the chemical composition of the Small Magellanic Cloud

Alice Minelli

Dipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia - Alma Mater Studiorum Università degli Studi di Bologna

Via Gobetti 93/2, I-40129 Bologna, Italy

INAF - Osservatorio di Astrofisica e Scienza dello Spazio di Bologna

Via Gobetti 93/3, I-40129 Bologna, Italy

The Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC) is an excellent laboratory to investigate the chemical enrichment history of a galaxy that has experienced strong gravitational interactions with other systems, since it is in an early stage of a minor merger event with the Large Magellanic Cloud. Despite its proximity (~ 60 kpc) and the possibility to resolve its stellar content, the chemical composition of the SMC is still poorly known. In order to fill this gap and to accurately reconstruct the chemical evolution of the stellar populations in the SMC, we analysed FLAMES@VLT high-resolution spectra of about 200 red giant stars belonging to the SMC field. Additionally, we analysed stars that are members of three SMC clusters with different ages (≈ 11 , ≈ 6 , and ≈ 1 Gyr), covering the entire range of ages of the SMC clusters system. This data-set allows to reconstruct the role played by the different contributors to the chemical enrichment, i.e. Type II and Ia supernovae, hypernovae, and AGB stars. In particular, most of the stars (both in the field and in clusters) have solar-scaled $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ ratios, indicating that they formed from a gas already polluted by Type Ia supernovae. Among the field stars, we identified a bunch of rare SMC metal-poor stars ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$) that allow to study the early chemical enrichment of the galaxy. Finally, we found evidence of a metallicity gradient within the SMC, with metallicity decreasing moving outward.

The Small Magellanic Cloud

The SMC is on a early stage of a minor merger with the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC) [1] and, together, they are on a first approach to the Milky Way (MW) [2]. These gravitational interactions influence the star formation of the galaxy with numerous bursts connected to the close passages between the Clouds [3]. The star formation is still ongoing in the SMC.

Analysed targets

We analysed both field and globular clusters (GCs) stars in the SMC. About 200 field stars have been observed around three GCs located in different regions of the galaxy. The stars were picked from the Gaia CMDs, selecting those located in the bright portion of the red giant branch. The three GCs were chosen in order to cover the entire range of ages of the SMC GCs, and 20 stars are observed among them. Both field and cluster samples have been obtained with high resolution FLAMES@VLT spectra. The two samples give complementary information, since field stars provide high statistics and the metallicity in different locations of the galaxy, allowing us to study the evolution of the chemistry with the po-

sition. Instead, GCs provide simultaneously the age and the metallicity of the stars, allowing us to study the evolution of the chemistry with the time.

Spectral analysis

The spectral analysis was made in a homogeneous way for both samples, in order to erase the presence of systematics due to different methods. This means that the analysis was made using the same approach to derive the chemical abundances, the same atomic data and model atmosphere and the same solar value. In this way, a difference in the chemical abundances had to be attributed to a real difference in the chemical composition of the stars.

Results

The study of the field stars sample leads to the following results:

- (1) the total metallicity distribution (Figure 1) shows a peak at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -1$ dex, as previously derived from low resolution study [5], with a tail at low metallicity;
- (2) the metallicity distribution changes with the location in the galaxy, in particular the peak value remains nearly constant, but moving toward the external region of the galaxy, the fraction of metal poor stars increases;
- (3) 12 stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$ dex are detected;

Figure 1: Total metallicity distribution of the field stars.

- (4) the α -elements abundance ratios of the SMC field stars (Figure 2) are lower with respect to the MW stars with similar metallicity. This difference is explained by a slower star formation rate of the SMC in comparison to the MW. Moreover, the hydrostatic α -elements (O and Mg), synthesized in stars with masses $M > 30 M_{\odot}$, are

more depleted than the explosive α -elements (Si, Ca and Ti), produced in stars with masses $15 M_{\odot} < M < 25 M_{\odot}$. The difference is explained with a lower contribution by massive stars in the chemical enrichment history of the SMC in comparison to the MW.

The results obtained from the chemical abundances of stars belonging to the three GCs of different ages are: (1) the metallicity of the stars, combined with their ages, confirms the age-metallicity relation previously derived theoretically by [4]. In particular, in the first 2 Gyr, the

SMC reached a metallicity of about -1.2 dex, keeping this value constant at least until 6 Gyr ago. Then, the metallicity started to increase, reaching a value of -0.6 dex, 1.5 Gyr ago.

(2) The three GCs have solar scaled α -elements abundances, another indication of a slower star formation rate of the SMC with respect to the MW.

(3) No evidence of multiple stellar populations is found from Na and O abundances of the analysed targets.

From the comparison between the metallicity of the field stars and the ones of the GCs, we can suppose that the most metal poor stars were formed in the first 1-2 Gyr (green shadow in Figure 3). From these stars, we can derive information on the early chemical enrichment history of the SMC. Moreover, the bulk of the field stars sample, peaked at -1 dex, were likely formed around 3-4 Gyr ago (green shadow in Figure 3), the epoch of the first encounter between the Clouds [1], which probably reactivated the star formation in the SMC.

Figure 2: Behaviour of the hydrostatic and explosive $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ abundance ratio (top and bottom panel, respectively) as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for SMC field stars (light blue) and MW literature data (grey).

Figure 3: Age-metallicity relation in the top panel for SMC GCs compared with the theoretical model of [4]. In the bottom panel, $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ abundance ratio as a function of the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for the SMC GCs (colored squares), SMC field stars (black dots) and MW literature data (grey dots).

References

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Short CV

2016: Bachelor degree in Astronomy, University of Bologna, Italy
 2018: Master degree in Astrophysics and Cosmology, University of Bologna, Italy
 2018-present: PhD in Astrophysics, University of Bologna, Italy